

Particle Swarm Optimization Based PID Power System Stabilizer for a Synchronous Machine

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Abstract : This paper proposes a swarm intelligence method that yields optimal Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) Controller parameters of a power system stabilizer (PSS) in a single machine infinite bus system. The proposed method utilizes the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm approach to generate the optimal tuning parameters. The paper is modeled in the MATLAB Simulink Environment to analyze the performance of a synchronous machine under several load conditions. At the same operating point, the PID-PSS parameters are also tuned by Ziegler-Nichols method. The dynamic performance of proposed controller is compared with the conventional Ziegler-Nichols method of PID tuning controller to demonstrate its advantage. The analysis reveals the effectiveness of the proposed PSO based PID controller.

Keywords : Particle Swarm Optimization, PID Controller, Power System Stabilizer

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